

INFLUENCING FACTORS FOR AN ONLINE CONSOLIDATING THERMOPLASTIC TAPE PLACEMENT PROCESS

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SUMMARY

Process parameter effects like heating, layup velocity, consolidation force; and tool temperature, were studied in terms of final mechanical strength. Simulations were performed to predict and to improve the procedure. Material properties are found out to support the simulation and manufacturing process.

Keywords: Tape Placement Process, Thermoplastic, Consolidation

INTRODUCTION

Fast layup and in-situ consolidation capabilities had allowed thermoplastic tape placement techniques to gain considerable appreciation in aerospace and automobile industries. Extensive research had been carried out side by side in theoretical and experimental aspects to realize a tape placement head for producing components with ideal mechanical properties [1]. Experimental parametric studies [2] were carried out for the improvement of placement settings. Theoretical models explaining the phenomenal process changes have been developed and implemented [3, 4, 5]. Investigations in the tape placement process are still underway to achieve the laminate's quality compared to other highly developed composite manufacturing setups, e.g. autoclave. Extensive work was also performed in the same direction at Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe (IVW) and evaluation of material mechanical performances revealed regions where up-gradation can bring significant enhancement [6]. This study encompasses issues like material properties characterization; tracing interlaminar bond development and search for optimized process parameters.

MATERIAL AND PROCESS CHARACTERIZATION

Surface Roughness and Intimate Contact

The thermoplastic material used in this study is the CF-PEEK tape from Suprem with a thickness of 0.13 mm and a width of 12 mm. The surface roughness profile from white light profilometry in width direction (Figure 1) indicates the statistically similar characteristic also known as self affine structure. Yang and Pitchumani proposed a model [4] by incorporating volume conservation and representation of a rough tape as an effective fractal surface which is flattened down to ideally smooth by rigid counter surface. Tracing the change in the contact area between effective fractal surface and rigid counter surface leads to the following equation for degree of intimate contact D_{ic} .

$$D_{ic}^{(n)}(t) = \frac{1}{f^n} \left[\frac{5}{4} \left(\frac{h_r}{L_r} \right)^2 \frac{f^{\frac{2nD}{2-D} + n + 4}}{(f+1)^2} \int_{t_{n+1}}^t \frac{P_{app}}{\eta_{fm}} dt + 1 \right]^{1/5} \quad \text{where } t_{n+1} \leq t \leq t_n$$

Where D is the fractal dimension, f is the scaling ratio, n is the no. of asperities generations, L_r is the total length for cantor set, P_{app} and t are applied pressure and duration under roller, η_{fm} is the fiber matrix viscosity and h_r is recess depth of first generation asperity. The slope of the profile's power spectrum on log-log plot gives the fractal dimension as $D = 1.3$ for the tape used in this study.

Figure 1: Surface roughness profile and fractal dimension (D) through its power spectrum

Fiber-matrix Viscosity

CF-PEEK thermoplastic exhibits relatively high longitudinal viscosity compared to transverse viscosity for unidirectional tapes. Taking the advantage of this behavior and assuming conservation of volume, the fiber-matrix viscosity η_{fm} can be related to the change in thickness dimension (h_o, h_f) of the samples [7], when compressed with force F between the hot plates at different high temperatures T for time duration t .

$$\eta_{fm} = \frac{5}{8} \frac{Ft}{L_o W_o^3} \frac{h_o^2 h_f^2}{h_o^5 - h_f^5}$$

Where L_o and W_o are initial length and width of sample Figure 2 shows the measured viscosity for under investigation thermoplastic material at different temperatures. The corresponding semi-empirical Arrhenius relation is

$$\eta_{fm} = A \exp^{B/T}$$

where $A = 643 \text{ N s/m}^2$ and $B = 4367 \text{ K}$.

Figure 2 : CF-PEEK thermoplastic viscosity as a function of temperature

Figure 3: Weld time determination for PEEK 150 PF materials at 340°C

Molecular Mobility and Interfacial Healing

As the asperities of the rough surface come into intimate contact, healing of the interface occurs through the polymer chain diffusion and entanglement with the other polymer chain. Complete healing depends on the molecular structure of the polymer and factors such as time, temperature and pressure at interface. According to reptations theory, the weld time t_w (or healing time) should be directly related to the longest molecular relaxation time in polymer melt. The evolution of non-isothermal degree of healing D_h with time is given by following expression [4]

$$D_h = \left[\int_0^t \frac{1}{t_w(T)} dt \right]^{1/4}$$

The relaxation time can be extracted from the viscosity/shear rate data obtained in steady state shear experiments. The viscosity of melted polymer follows Newtonian behavior at low shear rates, but then beyond a particular shear rate it begins to decrease with shear rate. The time constant associated with the onset of non-linear behavior of the viscosity is of the same magnitude as the longest relaxation time, see Figure 3. Experiments were carried out with PEEK 150PF grade material on parallel plate rheometer for the determination of relaxation time above melt temperature at 340, 360, 380 and 400 °C with 2% strain to develop Arrhenius relation as follow

$$t_w(T) = 2 \times 10^{-5} \exp^{43000/(RT)}$$

where R is universal gas constant.

Thermal Stability of PEEK Matrix

Thermal stability of the PEEK material in air is characterized by monitoring the changes in its viscosity with time through rheological experiments at different isotherm with 2% strain and 2.5 rad/sec shear rates. Figure 4 indicates the increase in the dynamic viscosity η' which is related to permanent changes in the resin properties due to morphological changes. It is [8] suggested that the mechanisms responsible for increase in viscosity consist of a homolitic

random chain scission process, producing radicals that attacks the neighboring polymer chain to form branches and finally crosslink. Crosslinking concentration for the non-isothermal process represents the crosslinking events per unit mass is given by following semi-empirical relation [9]

$$Rr = A \int_{330ini}^{330final} \exp\left[\frac{-E_a}{R.T(t)}\right] dt$$

where $A = 5 \times 10^{13}$ mol/(g-sec) and $E_a = 276$ KJ/mol for the PEEK material under investigation.

Figure 4: Viscosity variation with time for PEEK material

TAPE PLACEMENT PROCESS AND ITS MODELLING

A brief description of tape placement process is as follows: the incoming thermoplastic tape after passing through the guided assembly heats up with the help of hot gas torch and is placed at the hot tool with the help of a temperature controlled consolidation roller. Several tapes can be placed side by side and the laminate can be manufactured by placing additional layers over the previously laid up layers.

The layup process is the combination of different interdependent phenomenon. Heat transfer under the hot gas torch causes the drop in the tape viscosity making it suitable for void compression and intimate contact process under the roller. As soon the intimate contact occurs, healing of the interfaces begins and provides the degree of bond strength (D_b) between the layers.

$$D_b = D_{ic} \cdot D_h$$

EXPERIMENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Variation of Gas Volume Flow and Process Velocity

Series of 15 layered laminate plates are manufactured with the combination of different process velocity and hot gas flow volume through the torch. Samples from these plates were

tested for the interlaminar shear strength, see Figure 5. It is evident that lower process velocity generates laminates with higher shear strength, but after achieving some maxima in each case, the shear strength starts to drop down with increasing gas volume. The trends indicate some sort of degradation in laminate quality for higher gas volume. It means, for every process velocity there is a combination of hot gas volume flow, beyond which no further improvement is achievable.

Figure 5: Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) at different process layup velocities for 15 layered laminates, tool temperature is 280°C

It is suggested that the evaluation of the bonding degree can provide possible explanation for this behavior. Figure 6 shows the peel resistance for the two layer samples manufactured with process velocity of 3, 5 and 8 m/min with increasing gas volume flow. The corresponding simulated degrees of bonding curves are also plotted which fortified its accuracy by predicting the correct trend with the experiments. In all cases, $D_b < 100\%$ indicates the incomplete bonding for the two ply samples which can be improved if reworked with further layup cycles. If the similar calculations are carried out for the 15 layered laminates, the final degree of bonding can be traced. To cover the wide range of two parameter combinations, iso-curves are generated for the final average degree of bonding and corresponding crosslinking as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6: Peel resistance and corresponded simulated bonding degree D_b

Interesting observations are: slope of D_b iso-curves are steeper at lower velocities and tends to flatten at higher velocities, hence high bonding strength can be achievable at lower velocity.

Maximum achievable $D_b < 100\%$, indicates lack of capabilities of tape placement process to accomplish full bonding in laminates (this will be discussed in the next section). The crosslinking iso-curves have constant slope for larger groups of combination. Now the question arises, since several combinations are possible for particular D_b , which is most appropriate?

Major drop in the shear strength takes place between gas volume 6 Ltr/min and 8 Ltr/min in Figure 5. Considering the highest layup process velocity 9m/min which is subjected to minimum thermal exposure, the iso-crosslinking curve passes between these two locations in Figure 7 has a value of 10^{-4} mol/g. This curve indicates the limit below which the crosslinking effect is not prominent, while all the combination above will have sinking effect in strength due to higher crosslinking of polymer chain. Experimental D_b values were plotted over the plot in Figure 7 to confirm this finding. Maximum attainable experimental D_b is 91% for 3m/min, when it is under the cross linking curve, but with increasing hot gas volume, the fluctuation starts to appear as combination shifted above the iso-crosslinking curve. Analogous behavior is also visible for other velocity and gas flow combinations. So, for particular D_b , only those combinations are permissible which are not affected by the crosslink phenomenon. In such way laminates can have a better chance for further improvements such as reconsolidation passes as discussed further ahead.

Figure 7: Iso-curve for degree of bonding (D_b) and crosslinking rate (R_r)

Effect of Tool Temperature

Degrees of bonding through thickness are plotted for the laminate manufactured with different tool temperatures in Figure 8a. Cold tool behave as the heat sink and restrict bonding process in the early layers. Possible cause is the insufficient drop in viscosity to achieve full void compression and intimate contact. With the increased tool temperature significant

improvement is visible by reaching almost maximum value ($D_b=100\%$) within these layers. Shear strength test in Figure 8b for the plate manufactured with different tool temperatures also indicate better values at higher temperature. The increasing strength tendency is considerable till 280°C (which is the cooling crystallization temperature) to achieve complete bonding in early layers, after that no major improvement is noticeable.

Figure 8: (a) Tool temperature vs. layer wise degree of bonding (D_b) (b) corresponding ILSS and transverse tensile strength. Gas Volume 8 Ltr/min, Process velocity 3m/min

Reconsolidation Passes

As mentioned above, the degree of intimate contact plays an important role in achieving higher bonding degrees. Figure 9a shows how D_{ic} in the first layer reaches its final values after several successive passes. This gives an idea to improve the D_b in the top layers, consider the layup with a gas flow volume of 6 Ltr/min and a velocity of 3m/min, and a tool temperature of 280°C . At the end of the layup session, top most layers are reconsolidated by three additional passes with hot gas but no further layup. Figure 9b, shows the gradual improvement in the laminate shear strength upto two passes. The photomicrograph in Figure 10 also indicates the elimination of intra and interlaminar voids for the top most layers after two passes. Further passes produced no significant effect; instead matrix charring appears on the top layer surface indicates the degradation due to repetitive exposure of the hot gas. Further work can be performed in this direction by reducing the gas volume for these reconsolidation passes.

(a)

(b)

Figure 9: (a) Accomplishment of final intimate contact (D_{ic}) in first layer, and (b) effect of reconsolidation passes on interlaminar shear strength (ILSS)

(a)

(b)

Figure 10: Photomicrograph indicating the improvement in interlaminar bonding for top layers (a) without reconsolidation pass (b) with two reconsolidation passes

Effect of Consolidation Force

Simulation indicates the noteworthy improvement in shear strength with the increase in consolidation force from 50 to 160N as in Figure 11 (gas vol. 6 Ltr/min, vel. 3m/min, tool temp. 280°C). The enhancement trend levels off for higher forces. Unfortunately, due to high force limitation on existing equipment, shear strength tests were carried out for plates manufactured at 100N, 160N and 225N to examine this effect. Indeed the consolidation force under the roller is directly related to the interlaminar contact development but it also increases the internal void pressure of the trapped air between the layers. Thus very high forces are requires for significant improvement making the construction of tape placement head assembly heavier.

Figure 11: Consolidation force vs ILSS

Figure 12: Degree of intimate contact development with different surface roughnesses

Effect of Surface Roughness

Simulation results for intimate contact development for laminates manufactured with tape material of highly rough surface ($D = 1.8$), moderately rough surface ($D = 1.4$) and relatively smooth surface ($D = 1.2$) is shown in Figure 12. Evident is the rapid achievement of higher intimate contact through out the laminate with smooth surface tape and hence tape with flat surface could attain higher degree of bonding in tape placement process.

Figure 13: Transverse bonding between the tapes (a) tool at 250°C (b) tool at 280°C

Transverse Tensile Test

To investigate the bonding between the adjacent tapes, tensile test perpendiculars to fiber direction is carried out. Aforementioned variations are also explored for this test. Consider the effect of tool temperature in Figure 8b, representing low tensile strength at relatively cold tool and higher strength at 280°C and 300°C. Photomicrograph for these cases in Figure 13 shows the distant fiber bundles for the adjacent tow and larger matrix bonded areas for

laminates near the cold tool. Transverse expansion and fiber motion due to squeeze flow under the roller is the most influencing factor in this case. Improvement can be performed by estimating the width change through fiber matrix viscosity relation mentioned earlier to position the placement head for proper sidewise bonding.

CONCLUSION

The study presents existing challenges to achieve full consolidation through tape placement process. Due to short span of consolidation under the roller, intimate contact between the layers gets its final values in several passes, hence the top layers always lack full degree of bonding. Surface roughness data described by fractal in simulation indicates that tape material with smooth surface could generate high strength laminates. Improvements in the process setup to attain high laminate qualities were also identified. For each improvement a trend of significant improvement up to a certain level is detected, beyond which either no further rise or drop in laminate qualities starts to appear.

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Reference

- 1- G. Beresheim, Thermoplast-Tapelegen -ganzheitliche Prozessanalyse und -entwicklung. Kaiserslautern: IVW-Schriftenreihe Band 32 2002.
- 2- J.P. Kilroy, C.M.O' Brádaigh, C.O.A. Semprimoschnig, "Mechanical and Physical Evaluation of New Carbon Fibre/Peek Composites for Space Applications", SAMPE Journal, Volume 44, No.3 May/June 2008.
- 3- S. Ranganathan, S.G. Advani, M.A. Laminotia, "A Non-isothermal Model for Consolidation and Void Reduction during In-Situ Tow Placement of Thermoplastic Composites", Journal of Composite Materials, Vol.29, No.8, 1995.
- 4- F. Yang and R. Pitchumani, "Nonisothermal Healing and Interlaminar Bond Strength Evolution during Thermoplastic Matrix Composites Processing", Polymer Composites, April 2003, Vol 24, No.2.
- 5- M. Latrille, Prozessanalyse und -simulation von Verarbeitungsverfahren für faserverstärkte thermoplastische Bändchenhalbzeuge. Kaiserslautern: IVW-Schriftenreihe Band 40 2003.
- 6- R. Schledjewski, "Thermoplastic Tape Placement-Challenging the Autoclave Process" Proc. 1st European Conference on Materials and Structures in Aerospace (EUCOMAS), May 2008.
- 7- H.R. Lin and S.G. Advani, "Processing Models and Characterization of Thermoplastic Composite Wound Parts", Polymer Composites, June 1997, Vol 18, No. 3.
- 8- R. Philips, T. Glauser, J.E. Manson, "Thermal Stability of PEEK/Carbon Fiber in Air and Its Influence on Consolidation", Polymer Composites, Aug. 1997, Vol 18, No. 4.
- 9- C. Nicodeau, et al, "In-Situ Consolidation Process Optimization for Thermoplastic Matrix Composites," SAMPE 2006, Long Beach, CA, April 30 – May 4, 2006.